

Derivation of the position resolution of a muon stability monitoring system

monitoring system

Figure 1 illustrates the placement of scintillator detector placement in a muon-based stability monitoring system.

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of a muon stability system

Figure 2 Illustration of the least square method. k is the slope of the track, and b is the intercept.

The muon track on a telescope is fitted as shown in figure 2. χ^2 is defined as follows:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \left(\frac{x_{\text{rec},i} - x_{\text{rea},i}}{\sigma_i} \right)^2, \quad (1)$$

where the integer i is the order of the detector planes, $x_{\text{rec},i}$ is the reconstructed hit position, $x_{\text{rea},i}$ is the real hit position and σ_i is the position resolution of the i -th detector layer. Because of $x = kz + b$ and $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \sigma_3$, we can simplify this equation as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^3 (kz_i + b - x_i)^2, \quad (2)$$

The following formula can be obtained by taking the partial derivative of χ^2 .

$$k = \frac{\sum z_i x_i \sum 1 - \sum z_i \sum x_i}{\sum z_i^2 \sum 1 - (\sum z_i)^2}, \quad (3a)$$

$$b = \frac{\sum z_i^2 \sum x_i - \sum z_i \sum z_i x_i}{\sum z_i^2 \sum 1 - (\sum z_i)^2}. \quad (3b)$$

In this study, $z_1 = -D$, $z_2 = 0$ and $z_3 = D$. D is the distance between detector planes. k and b can be expressed as:

$$k = \frac{x_3 - x_1}{2D}, \quad (4a)$$

$$b = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3}{3}. \quad (4b)$$

According to the propagation scheme of uncertainties, the standard deviation and covariance of k and b can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_k^2 & \sigma_{kb} \\ \sigma_{bk} & \sigma_b^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_2} & \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_3} \\ \frac{\partial b}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial b}{\partial x_2} & \frac{\partial b}{\partial x_3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{x_1}^2 & \sigma_{x_1 x_2} & \sigma_{x_1 x_3} \\ \sigma_{x_2 x_1} & \sigma_{x_2}^2 & \sigma_{x_2 x_3} \\ \sigma_{x_3 x_1} & \sigma_{x_3 x_2} & \sigma_{x_3}^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial b}{\partial x_1} \\ \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_2} & \frac{\partial b}{\partial x_2} \\ \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_3} & \frac{\partial b}{\partial x_3} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma_{x_1}^2 = \sigma_{x_2}^2 = \sigma_{x_3}^2 = \sigma_{w,s}^2$ and $\sigma_{x_1 x_2} = \sigma_{x_2 x_1} = \sigma_{x_1 x_3} = \sigma_{x_3 x_1} = \sigma_{x_2 x_3} = \sigma_{x_3 x_2} = 0$. As a result, we can get eq.6 and eq.7(a-b) combining eq.(4a-b) and eq.(5).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_k^2 & \sigma_{kb} \\ \sigma_{bk} & \sigma_b^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2D} & 0 & -\frac{1}{2D} \\ \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{w,s}^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{w,s}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{w,s}^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2D} & \frac{1}{3} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{3} \\ -\frac{1}{2D} & \frac{1}{3} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_k = \frac{\sigma_{w,s}}{\sqrt{2D}}, \quad (7a)$$

$$\sigma_b = \frac{\sigma_{w,s}}{\sqrt{3}}. \quad (7b)$$